

Toxicity And Pharmacokinetics Of Lithium Ascorbate

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Abstract

Lithium salts are established pharmacological agents in psychiatry, but their clinical use is limited by concerns about toxicity, narrow therapeutic range, and the need for blood-level monitoring. Lithium ascorbate, an organic lithium salt, has been proposed as a potentially lower-toxicity lithium-containing compound, but its toxicological and pharmacokinetic profile requires systematic evaluation. This study assessed the toxicity and pharmacokinetics of lithium ascorbate in rabbits, mice, and rats using repeated-dose, acute-dose, cumulative-toxicity, and tissue-distribution experiments. In rabbits, repeated intragastric administration at doses up to 150 mg/kg for 180 days produced no signs of chronic systemic toxicity or local irritation. In acute intragastric studies, toxicity occurred only at high doses, with LD50 values of 6140 mg/kg in male mice, 6920 mg/kg in female mice, 4810 mg/kg in male rats, and 5070 mg/kg in female rats. Acute intravenous administration in rats caused no mortality up to 3000 mg/kg, while higher doses produced systemic toxicity and dose-associated local vascular injury. Repeated escalating intragastric dosing in male rats showed moderate cumulative toxicity, with a cumulation coefficient of 3.74. Pharmacokinetic analysis after intragastric administration showed rapid absorption, broad tissue distribution, and prolonged lithium retention in blood and frontal brain tissue. Overall, lithium ascorbate demonstrated low-to-moderate preclinical toxicity, supporting further comparative, mechanistic, and translational safety studies before conclusions about human dosing or clinical safety can be made.

Keywords: lithium ascorbate; toxicity; pharmacokinetics; preclinical safety; psychiatry; animal studies

Introduction

Lithium salts are used in psychiatry as an efficient treatment of mental disorders, such as bipolar disorder and major depressive disorder.

Despite the efficiency of lithium and its recommended use as a first-line therapy for bipolar disorder, prescription rates of lithium went down globally, including the U.S., Europe, and Asia (Kessing, 2024). The trend seems to be unique for lithium as other bipolar disorder medications' prescription rates, such as antipsychotics and antiepileptics, have increased (Kessing, 2024). For the United States, from 2017 to 2022, shows that lithium was prescribed only to 27% of patients with bipolar disorder (Steger et al., 2025).

There are several possible reasons why lithium prescription rates are declining. First, lithium is seen as a “toxic drug” due to its rare side effects, affecting thyroid and renal functions (McKnight et al., 2012, Gitlin, 2016; Rybakowski, 2018; Kessing, 2024). Second, lithium treatment requires blood testing to monitor lithium levels in blood due to its narrow therapeutic window (Baumgartner et al., 1997; Gitlin, 2016; Fiorillo et al, 2023). Third, less experienced

psychiatrists may prefer other mood stabilizers that are considered more manageable and less toxic (Fiorillo et al, 2023). Authors offer educational strategies to improve lithium's image among both clinicians and patients.

Another option is to test and use other forms of lithium that are effective and have a better safety profile. For example, an Alzheimer's study by Aron et al. (2025) showed that organic lithium salts, such as lithium orotate, have lower conductivity compared to inorganic salts and don't bind to amyloid plaques, making more lithium available in non-plaque brain tissue. Potentially, the lower doses of organic lithium salts can be tested and advertised as an alternative to "scary" lithium carbonate.

Lithium Ascorbate

One of the latest developments in terms of lithium salts on the pharmacological market is lithium ascorbate (Torshin et al., 2022). By Normopharm. Lithium ascorbate is an organic salt of lithium and ascorbic acid (Vitamin C).

Lithium ascorbate is a lower-toxicity lithium salt with reported anxiolytic, antidepressant, neuroprotective, and memory-supporting effects, and its effects may be achieved at lower doses than lithium carbonate (Torshin et al., 2022; Rastashanskiy, 2020; Rastashanskiy & Ostrenko, 2020)

Lithium ascorbate could offer therapeutic effects with a wider safety margin, but its toxicity, and pharmacokinetics must be studied to understand what the therapeutic window is and how it is absorbed and distributed in the body.

Chemoreactonic modeling was used to select lithium ascorbate as the lead lithium salt for subsequent experimental studies. The screening included sequential evaluation of 1,245 water-soluble organic lithium salts for acute toxicity, bioavailability and pharmacokinetic parameters, and predicted pharmacodynamic effects. This process identified 38 minimally toxic salts, of which 11 showed bioavailability above 20% (Torshin et al., 2022).

Further analysis of pharmacological profiles and potential interactions with human proteome targets indicated that lithium ascorbate had the most favorable overall profile, including predicted antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroactive, and GSK-3 β inhibitory properties. On this basis, lithium ascorbate was selected for synthesis and further investigation in neurocytological, biodistribution, toxicity, antitumor, adaptogenic, and neuroprotective studies (Torshin et al., 2022).

The tested drug developer and the organization responsible for arranging the preclinical studies is Normopharm LLC. The studies were performed in accordance with GLP OECD principles (OECD, 1998a).

The test substance was Lithium Ascorbate, substance code T-1.28/21, supplied by Normopharm LLC, Russia. The substance was manufactured according to Good Manufacturing Practice. The control substance was listed as vehicle code M-1.28/21; saline solution, Grotex LLC, Russia.

Study 1: Chronic toxicity on rabbits with the evaluation of local irritant effect

Material and methods

The study was performed by the Laboratory of Drug Toxicology of the Federal State Budgetary Scientific Institution “Institute of Toxicology of the Federal Medical from 3 August 2018 to 21 June 2019 under protocol PCS 12/18-2.

The study was designed to evaluate the chronic 180-day toxicity of Lithium Ascorbate, followed by an additional 30-day delayed observation period after the end of exposure, and an additional assessment of the local irritant effect (OECD, 2018).

Sexually mature chinchilla rabbits aged 3 months were used as the model species (OECD, 1998b). The animals received the test substance or the control substance by repeated oral administration through a gavage tube.

Lithium Ascorbate was administered at three dose levels: 5.0 mg/kg, 50.0 mg/kg, and 150 mg/kg. The individual administration volume for each animal was calculated according to body weight and adjusted after each weighing.

During the exposure period and delayed observation period, the animals were monitored for clinical signs of intoxication, body weight dynamics, water consumption, feed consumption, physiological parameters, hematological parameters, and biochemical parameters (OECD, 2018). Urine parameters were also assessed. Biological materials were collected for laboratory analysis according to the study schedule. At necropsy, internal organs were examined macroscopically, organ mass coefficients were calculated and compared, and tissue samples were collected for microscopic examination. The study also included an assessment of the local irritant effect of the test substance (European Medicines Agency, 2015).

Results

Repeated use of lithium ascorbate up to 150 mg/kg for 180 days did not produce signs of chronic systemic toxicity. Body weight of animals increased uniformly in control and treated groups, and no treatment-related changes were observed in clinical condition, water or feed consumption, rectal temperature, electrocardiographic parameters, urinalysis, hematology, or blood biochemistry.

Postmortem examination did not reveal visible pathological changes in internal organs, and organ mass coefficients showed no toxicologically significant deviations. Macroscopic and microscopic examination did not identify treatment-related tissue lesions or evidence of local irritant action.

Study 2: Toxic properties following a single intragastric administration to mice

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at CJSC “Saint Petersburg Institute of Pharmacy” under study code 1.28/21. The final report was approved on September 13, 2021. The work was conducted in accordance with GLP OECD principles (OECD, 1998a).

Sexually mature outbred mice were used as the model species. The test system included 60 animals, consisting of 30 males and 30 females. Animals were allocated into six experimental groups, with five males and five females in each group. The control group received the control substance, while the treatment groups received Lithium Ascorbate at escalating doses.

The study was designed as an acute single-dose intragastric toxicity experiment with assessment of systemic toxicity, mortality, clinical signs of intoxication, local irritant action, and median lethal dose, LD50.

Lithium Ascorbate was administered once, in fractions, by the intragastric route at doses of 4000, 5000, 6000, 7000, and 8000 mg/kg (Diehl et al., 2001). The control animals received the control substance using the same intragastric route. The dosing volume was 32 mL/kg (Diehl et al., 2001).

The total observation period was 15 days. The test substance or control was administered on Day 1. Body weight was recorded on Days 1, 2, 8, and 15. Clinical examination was performed before dosing and on Days 2, 8, and 14, while clinical observation was conducted from before dosing through Days 1–15. All surviving animals were euthanized on Day 15.

Biological material collection was performed during post-mortem examination. Internal organs were examined macroscopically, and organ mass coefficients were calculated. The gastrointestinal tract, especially the gastric mucosa, was evaluated for signs of local irritant action, including hemorrhages, erosive-ulcerative lesions, epithelial desquamation, and other visible pathological changes. Euthanasia and planned necropsy was performed in surviving animals at the end of the observation period, while unplanned necropsy was performed in animals that died during the study.

Results

A single intragastric administration of lithium ascorbate produced dose-dependent acute toxicity at high doses of 4000–8000 mg/kg. Mortality increased with dose and was mainly delayed, occurring predominantly 3–5 days after administration. The calculated LD50 was 6140 ± 319 mg/kg in males and 6920 ± 426 mg/kg in females, indicating slightly lower sensitivity in females compared with males.

Clinical and postmortem findings supported a dose-related toxic response after high-dose exposure, while the available study summary did not indicate toxic effects in the control group. Based on the calculated LD50 values, Lithium Ascorbate was classified as GHS/OECD hazard category 5 for intragastric exposure (OECD, 2022).

Study 3: Toxic properties following a single intragastric administration to rats

Materials and Methods

The study was performed at CJSC “Saint Petersburg Institute of Pharmacy” under study code 2.28/21. The final report was approved in 2021.

The acute toxicity of Lithium Ascorbate was evaluated following a single administration to sexually mature rats. Sexually mature Wistar rats were used as the experimental model. The test system included 60 animals, consisting of 30 males and 30 females. Animals were distributed into six groups, with five males and five females in each group.

The study was designed as a single-dose acute toxicity experiment with assessment of systemic toxic effects, clinical signs of intoxication, mortality, local irritant action, and median lethal dose, LD50. Lithium Ascorbate was administered once, in fractions, at doses of 3000, 4000, 5000, 6000, and 7000 mg/kg. The control group received the control substance only.

The dosing volume was 32 mL/kg (Diehl et al., 2001). The observation period lasted 15 days after administration. The test substance or control was administered on Day 1. Body weight was recorded on Days 1, 2, 8, and 15. Clinical examination was performed before dosing and on Days 2, 8, and 14. Clinical observations were conducted from before dosing through Days 1–15. All surviving animals were euthanized on Day 15. Animals that died during the observation period underwent unscheduled necropsy.

Sampling and material collection were performed during post-mortem examination. Internal organs were collected and examined macroscopically. Organ mass coefficients were calculated. Particular attention was given to the gastrointestinal tract and gastric mucosa to assess local

irritant action. In animals that died before scheduled euthanasia, unplanned necropsy included evaluation of the stomach, small intestine, large intestine, lungs, brain and meninges, and other internal organs. In selected cases, histological examination was performed on intestinal tissues, including the small and large intestine, to evaluate epithelial necrosis, villous atrophy, submucosal edema, hemorrhage, and inflammatory infiltration.

The analysis included mortality rate, timing of death, clinical signs of intoxication, body weight dynamics, macroscopic pathological findings, organ mass coefficients, local irritant effects, and LD50 calculation.

Results

A single intragastric administration of Lithium Ascorbate to sexually mature Wistar rats produced no mortality or clinical signs of intoxication at 3000 mg/kg, which was identified as the maximum tolerated dose (OECD, 2022).

At 4000–7000 mg/kg, toxicity was dose-dependent and included depression of general condition, diarrhea, ruffled hair, nasal and ocular discharge, tremor, ataxia, reduced response to stimuli, and occasional ptosis. Mortality was mainly delayed and occurred predominantly 3–5 days after administration.

Necropsy of animals that died during the study revealed cerebral edema, pulmonary edema, internal organ congestion, gastric erosions, intestinal hemorrhages, and necrotic changes in the colonic mucosa, with evidence of local gastrointestinal irritant action at lethal doses. The LD50 was 4810 ± 386 mg/kg in males and 5070 ± 161 mg/kg in females.

Based on these values, Lithium Ascorbate was classified differently by sex according to the cited toxicity classifications: in males as a moderately toxic substance according to GHS/OECD hazard category 4; in females, as a low-toxic substance according to GHS/OECD hazard category 5 (OECD, 2022).

Study 4: The toxic properties following a single intravenous administration to sexually mature rats

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at CJSC “Saint Petersburg Institute of Pharmacy” under study code 3.28/21.

The acute toxicity of Lithium Ascorbate was evaluated following a single intravenous administration to sexually mature rats. Sexually mature Wistar rats were used as the model

species. The test system included 80 animals, consisting of 40 males and 40 females. Animals were assigned to eight groups, with five males and five females in each group.

The study was designed as a single-dose acute intravenous toxicity experiment with assessment of systemic toxic effects, mortality, clinical signs of intoxication, local tolerability at the injection site, and median lethal dose, LD50 (European Medicines Agency, 2015). Lithium Ascorbate was administered intravenously once, or fractionally when required by dose volume, at doses of 500, 1000, 2000, 3000, 3250, 3500, 3750, and 4000 mg/kg. The control group received saline solution by the same route.

The study dose range was adjusted during the experiment based on observed mortality: lower doses of 1000 and 2000 mg/kg caused no deaths, while 4000 mg/kg caused 100% mortality; additional dose groups were therefore introduced to refine LD50 estimation.

The test substance was administered via the intravenous route on Day 1. Administration volumes depended on dose and were based on a Lithium Ascorbate concentration of 125 mg/mL. The dosing volume ranged from 4 mL/kg at 500 mg/kg to 32 mL/kg at 4000 mg/kg (Diehl et al., 2001). Higher volumes were administered fractionally: 3000 mg/kg was administered as 24 mL/kg, 3250 mg/kg as 26 mL/kg, 3500 mg/kg as 28 mL/kg, 3750 mg/kg as 30 mL/kg, and 4000 mg/kg as 32 mL/kg (Diehl et al., 2001).

The total observation period was 15 days. Body weight was recorded on Days 1, 2, 8, and 15. Clinical examination was performed before dosing and on Days 2, 8, and 14. Clinical observations were conducted from the pre-dose period through Days 1–15. All surviving animals were euthanized on Day 15. Animals that died before scheduled euthanasia underwent unscheduled necropsy. The experimental part of the study began on August 10, 2021, and ended on October 11, 2021; the study was completed on November 8, 2021.

Material collection was performed during planned necropsy of surviving animals and unplanned necropsy of animals that died during the observation period. Internal organs were examined macroscopically, and organ mass coefficients were calculated. Particular attention was given to the caudal vein and surrounding tissues, as the study included assessment of local tolerability at the injection site. In selected animals, histological examination was performed on affected tissues, including the lungs, gastrointestinal tract, intestinal mucosa, and tissues surrounding the injection site.

The analysis included mortality, timing of death, clinical signs of intoxication, body weight dynamics, macroscopic pathological findings, organ mass coefficients, injection-site tolerability, and LD50 calculation.

Results

No mortality was observed at 500, 1000, 2000, or 3000 mg/kg. Mortality occurred at 3250 mg/kg in males, 3500 mg/kg in males, 3750 mg/kg in females, and 4000 mg/kg in both sexes. Death was predominantly delayed, occurring mainly 3–5 days after administration. The calculated LD50 was 3225 ± 95.2 mg/kg in males and 3625 ± 62.5 mg/kg in females.

Clinical signs of intoxication included ruffled hair, inhibition of general condition, discharge from the nose and eyes, tremor, shortness of breath, ataxia, ptosis, and altered response to stimuli. The severity and duration of these signs increased with dose. At 500 mg/kg, no signs of intoxication were recorded. At 1000 and 2000 mg/kg, transient signs were observed and resolved within several hours. At higher doses, signs persisted for several days and, in lethal groups, progressed until death.

Post-mortem findings in animals that died during the study included cerebral edema and plethora of the meninges, pulmonary edema, internal organ congestion, gastric and intestinal hemorrhages, watery intestinal contents, intestinal epithelial necrosis, and, in some cases, inflammatory changes in the lungs. The reported cause of death in all dead animals was acute heart failure. Routine necropsy of surviving animals generally did not reveal clinically significant pathological changes in internal organs, except for isolated findings such as splenic plethora in one female at 1000 mg/kg.

Assessment of local tolerability showed no macroscopically visible injection-site changes at 500 and 1000 mg/kg. At higher doses, local findings included fibroplasia around the injection site, hemorrhagic impregnation of tissues surrounding the caudal vein, thickening or congestion of the caudal vein, vascular thrombus, edema of the vein wall, neutrophilic infiltration, and vasculitis. These findings indicate dose-associated local vascular and perivascular effects after intravenous administration (Jochims et al., 2003).

Study 5: The accumulation of substance following repeated intragastric administration to rats

Materials and Methods

The study was performed at CJSC “Saint Petersburg Institute of Pharmacy” under study code 3.42/21. The study was reviewed by the Bioethics Commission for compliance with the Three Rs principles and Directive 2010/63/EU and was approved for conduct under approval No. BEC 3.42/21 dated August 23, 2021.

A repeated-dose cumulative toxicity study of Lithium Ascorbate was conducted in sexually mature rats to evaluate the cumulative toxic potential of the substance after repeated intragastric administration.

Sexually mature male Wistar rats were used as the experimental model. The study included one experimental group of 10 males.

The study was designed to assess cumulative toxicity by repeated intragastric administration of increasing doses of Lithium Ascorbate. The intended dose-escalation schedule consisted of doses corresponding to 0.1, 0.15, 0.22, 0.34, 0.5, 0.75, and 1.12 of the previously determined LD50 value (Tritek & Gulyaev, 2011). Each dose level was planned to be administered for four consecutive days before escalation to the next dose. The tested doses were 481 mg/kg from Days 1–4, 721.5 mg/kg from Days 5–8, 1058.2 mg/kg from Days 9–12, 1635.4 mg/kg from Days 13–16, and 2405 mg/kg from Days 17–20. The planned higher dose levels of 3607.5 mg/kg and 5387.2 mg/kg were not tested because all animals died by Day 21.

Lithium Ascorbate was administered repeatedly by the intragastric route. Administration was performed daily and, when necessary, fractionally. The dosing volume was 10 mL/kg for doses from 481 to 1635.4 mg/kg. For the 2405 mg/kg dose, the administration volume was 20 mL/kg, given as two 10 mL fractions. The concentration of the administered substance was adjusted according to dose.

The experimental part of the study began on September 28, 2021, and ended on October 17, 2021. The total actual duration of animal exposure was 21 days, although the original study plan included euthanasia on Day 29. Planned euthanasia was not performed because all animals died before the scheduled endpoint. Body weight was recorded on Day 1 and before each dose increase. Clinical examination was performed before administration and on Days 2, 8, and 14. Clinical observation was performed daily after administration of the test substance.

Sampling and material collection were performed during post-mortem examination of animals that died during the study. The collected and examined materials included internal organs and tissues relevant to systemic toxicity and cumulative injury. Pathomorphological examination included the brain and meninges, lungs, internal organs, adrenal glands, mesenteric lymph nodes, stomach, small intestine, large intestine, and pancreas. Particular attention was given to gastrointestinal tissues because macroscopic and microscopic lesions were observed in the stomach and intestines.

Results

Repeated intragastric administration of increasing doses of Lithium Ascorbate to male Wistar rats resulted in progressive toxic effects and complete mortality by Day 21. Clinical signs began on Day 10 and included ruffled hair, nasal discharge, and behavioral inhibition, followed by exhaustion, ataxia, tremor, and reduced response to stimuli during the later phase of exposure. Mortality began on Day 14 and occurred before the planned higher dose levels could be tested.

The LD50 after repeated administration was calculated as 17,989.4 mg/kg. The cumulation coefficient was calculated as $17,989.4/4810 = 3.74$, where 4810 mg/kg corresponded to the previously determined LD50 after a single intragastric administration in male rats. Based on this value, Lithium Ascorbate was classified as a substance with moderate cumulative properties, according to the criterion $3 < F_{cum} < 5$ (Tritek & Gulyaev, 2011).

Post-mortem examination showed cerebral edema and plethora of the brain membranes, internal organ plethora in all animals, and mild pulmonary edema in half of the animals. Gastrointestinal findings included hemorrhages in the gastric mucosa, erosive-ulcerative lesions of the glandular stomach, epithelial exfoliation with mononuclear infiltration, hemorrhages in the small and large intestines, blood in intestinal contents, and ulcerative defects of the small and large intestinal mucosa. Additional findings included focal hypertrophy of exocrine pancreatic cells, isolated adrenal hemorrhage, and mesenteric lymph node congestion. The reported cause of death in all animals was acute heart failure.

Study 6: Pharmacokinetics and compartmentalization

Materials and Methods

The study was performed in accordance with international rules for the handling of laboratory animals and was approved by the Ethics Committee of Ivanovo State Medical Academy on March 24, 2016.

A pharmacokinetic study of Lithium Ascorbate was conducted to evaluate lithium concentration dynamics and tissue compartmentalization after a single administration of the compound. The study assessed lithium levels in whole blood, urine, and tissue homogenates from multiple organs, with the aim of characterizing absorption, tissue distribution, retention, elimination, and potential lithium depot compartments.

Male Wistar white rats were used as the model species. The study included 54 animals weighing 200–250 g, divided into nine groups of six rats each.

The administered solution contained 250 µg of elemental lithium per 1 mL. The target dose was 1000 µg/kg, calculated based on elemental lithium. For a 250 g rat, this corresponded to 250 µg of elemental lithium, or 1 mL of the prepared solution. The individual administration volume was adjusted according to each animal's body weight. The document specifies that lithium ascorbate dihydrate contains lithium and ascorbate in a 1:1 molar ratio and a 1:71.33 mass ratio; therefore, 250 µg of elemental lithium corresponded to 17.84 mg of lithium ascorbate dihydrate.

The study was designed as a single-dose pharmacokinetic and tissue-distribution experiment. Lithium Ascorbate was administered by gastric gavage at a dose of 1000 µg/kg based on elemental lithium. This dose was selected as a 10-fold experimental dose relative to the

previously described 100 µg/kg exposure level used for longer-term administration and was stated to be far below the acutely toxic range.

Sampling was performed at nine time points after administration: 0 min, 45 min, 1 h, 1.5 h, 3 h, 6 h, 12 h, 24 h, and 48 h. At each time point, one group of six animals was selected for sample collection. The collected biosubstrates included whole blood, urine, brain, frontal lobe of the brain, heart, aorta, lungs, liver, kidneys, spleen, adrenal glands, and femur. Tissue samples were processed as homogenates for lithium quantification.

For analytical preparation, tissue homogenate samples were placed into plastic tubes and diluted fivefold with bidistilled and deionized water. Indium was added as an internal standard at a concentration of 25 µg/L. Calibration solutions were prepared using standard solutions with known lithium concentrations in the range of 5–1000 µg/L. Lithium concentrations were measured by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry using a Plasma Quad PQ2 Turbo mass spectrometer. Each sample was analyzed repeatedly, with three to ten exposures per sample and a signal integration time of 60 seconds.

The pharmacokinetic analysis included both non-compartmental and compartmental approaches. Non-compartmental analysis was performed using Excel spreadsheets supplemented with PKSolver modules (Zhang et al., 2010). The evaluated parameters included C_{max} , t_{max} , Cl_{ast} , AUC_t, MRT_t, terminal elimination slope, half-life, clearance, and volume of distribution. Compartmental pharmacokinetic modeling was performed using the SimBiology package in MATLAB 2016 (Ferreira, 2009). One-, two-, three-, and four-compartment models were compared to identify the model that best described lithium concentration dynamics in whole blood.

Results

After a single intragastric administration of Lithium Ascorbate to male Wistar rats at 1000 µg/kg calculated as elemental lithium, lithium was detected in whole blood, urine, and all examined tissues.

The analysis showed that lithium reached peak concentrations within approximately 1–1.5 h in most biosubstrates, while later peak times were observed in the spleen, adrenal glands, and femur.

Lithium concentrations in whole blood and the frontal lobe of the brain remained relatively stable for at least 40–45 h after peak concentration. The best-fitting compartmental model was a three-compartment model consisting of the gastrointestinal tract, whole blood as the central compartment, and a lithium depot compartment, with elimination occurring from the central compartment.

The model showed acceptable agreement with experimental blood data, with a standard deviation of 3.4 µg/L and a correlation coefficient of 0.92 between theoretical and observed concentrations.

Discussion

Lithium salts are used in psychiatry as an efficient treatment of mental disorders, such as bipolar disorder and major depressive disorder. However, lithium prescription rates are declining; one of the reasons is a persistent view of lithium as a toxic drug. One option to encounter the negative image of lithium is to research and use organic lithium salts.

One of the latest developments in terms of lithium salts on the pharmacological market is lithium ascorbate (Torshin et al., 2022). Lithium ascorbate is a lower-toxicity lithium salt with reported anxiolytic, antidepressant, neuroprotective, and memory-supporting effects (Torshin et al., 2022; Rastashanskiy, 2020; Rastashanskiy & Ostrenko, 2020).

Study 1 of toxicity in rabbits showed that repeated use of lithium ascorbate up to 150 mg/kg for 180 days did not produce signs of chronic systemic toxicity.

Study 2 of acute gastric toxicity in mice resulted in death at doses of 4000–8000 mg/kg. The calculated LD₅₀ was 6140 ± 319 mg/kg in males and 6920 ± 426 mg/kg in females. Lithium Ascorbate was classified as GHS/OECD hazard category 5 for intragastric exposure (OECD, 2022).

Study 3 of acute gastric toxicity in rats resulted in death at doses of 4000–7000 mg/kg. No mortality or intoxication signs were observed up to 3000 mg/kg. Lithium Ascorbate was classified in males as a moderately toxic substance according to GHS/OECD hazard category 4 and in females as a low-toxic substance according to GHS/OECD hazard category 5 (OECD, 2022).

Study 4 of acute toxicity via intravenous route of administration in rats showed no mortality at 500, 1000, 2000, or 3000 mg/kg. Mortality occurred at 3250 mg/kg in males, 3750 mg/kg in females. At 500 mg/kg, no signs of intoxication were recorded. At 1000 and 2000 mg/kg, transient signs were observed. Clinical signs of intoxication included ruffled hair, inhibition of general condition, discharge from the nose and eyes, tremor, shortness of breath, ataxia, ptosis, and altered response to stimuli. The severity and duration of these signs increased with dose. Assessment of local tolerability showed no macroscopically visible injection-site changes at 500 and 1000 mg/kg. At higher doses, local findings included fibroplasia around the injection site, hemorrhagic impregnation of tissues surrounding the caudal vein, thickening or congestion of the caudal vein, vascular thrombus, edema of the vein wall, neutrophilic infiltration, and vasculitis.

These findings indicate dose-associated local vascular and perivascular effects after intravenous administration.

Further, study 5 of repeated intragastric administration of increasing doses to rats resulted in progressive toxic effects and complete mortality. Clinical signs began on Day 10 and included ruffled hair, nasal discharge, and behavioral inhibition, followed by exhaustion, ataxia, tremor, and reduced response to stimuli during the later phase of exposure. The LD50 was calculated as 17,989.4 mg/kg. The cumulation coefficient was calculated as $17,989.4/4810 = 3.74$, where 4810 mg/kg corresponded to the previously determined LD50 after a single intragastric administration in male rats. Based on this value, Lithium Ascorbate was classified as a substance with moderate cumulative properties.

Post-mortem examination showed cerebral edema and plethora of the brain membranes, internal organ plethora in all animals, and mild pulmonary edema in half of the animals. Gastrointestinal findings included hemorrhages in the gastric mucosa, erosive-ulcerative lesions of the glandular stomach, epithelial exfoliation with mononuclear infiltration, hemorrhages in the small and large intestines, blood in intestinal contents, and ulcerative defects of the small and large intestinal mucosa. Additional findings included focal hypertrophy of exocrine pancreatic cells, isolated adrenal hemorrhage, and mesenteric lymph node congestion. The reported cause of death in all animals was acute heart failure.

Study 6 assessed pharmacokinetics and compartmentalization. After a single intragastric administration to rats at 1000 µg/kg calculated as elemental lithium, lithium was detected in whole blood, urine, and all examined tissues.

Pharmacokinetic data showed rapid absorption and broad tissue distribution of lithium after intragastric administration, with peak concentrations generally reached within 1–1.5 h and prolonged retention in whole blood and frontal brain tissue. The three-compartment model, including a depot compartment, is consistent with sustained lithium compartmentalization and may explain the observed cumulative toxicity during repeated dosing.

Overall, the toxicity studies indicate that lithium ascorbate has a relatively low acute toxicity profile after intragastric administration, with lethal effects occurring only at high doses in mice and rats. Repeated administration in rabbits at doses up to 150 mg/kg for 180 days did not produce signs of chronic systemic toxicity, supporting acceptable tolerability under prolonged exposure at lower doses. However, dose escalation studies in rats demonstrated progressive toxicity and complete mortality, with a calculated cumulation coefficient indicating moderate cumulative properties. Acute intravenous administration showed no mortality up to 3000 mg/kg, but higher doses produced dose-dependent systemic intoxication and local vascular or perivascular injury at the injection site. These findings suggest that lithium ascorbate has a comparatively wide safety margin at lower and moderate doses, but its toxic effects become pronounced with high-dose, repeated, or parenteral exposure.

Several limitations should be considered. Sample sizes were relatively small in several dose groups, which is common in acute toxicity testing but limits precision for sex-specific comparisons and uncommon adverse findings. The cumulative toxicity study used only male rats, and the pharmacokinetic study also used only male rats, limiting conclusions about female pharmacokinetics and cumulative toxicity.

The pharmacokinetic study measured lithium after administration of Lithium Ascorbate but did not include a direct comparison with lithium carbonate, lithium citrate, or lithium orotate. Therefore, differences in absorption, brain availability, tissue retention, and elimination among lithium salts remain unresolved.

Overall, the preclinical data indicate that Lithium Ascorbate was well tolerated after long-term oral administration in rabbits at doses up to 150 mg/kg and showed low-to-moderate acute toxicity only at high oral and intravenous doses in rodents. High-dose toxicity was associated mainly with neurological depression, gastrointestinal injury, edema, vascular congestion, and, after intravenous administration, local vascular irritation. Pharmacokinetic results suggest rapid absorption, broad tissue distribution, and possible depot-like retention. These findings support further investigation of Lithium Ascorbate as a lithium-containing compound with potential pharmacological utility, but additional standardized comparative, mechanistic, and translational studies are required before conclusions can be made about human safety, clinical dosing, or superiority over established lithium salts.

Data availability

All source data for this study are available upon reasonable request.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, Rastashanskiy V.V.; methodology, software, validation, formal analysis, data collection and investigation, resources, data curation, writing - original draft preparation Masterova K.V., Anisimova M.A., Popova A.V., Aleshanova N.A., Vasilyev A.V., Gushchin Y.A., Kishchenko N.A., Akimov D.Y.; writing - review and editing Gromova O.A.; supervision, project administration, Gromova O.A., Rastashanskiy V.V. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Ethics declarations

This research was conducted according to the GLP/OECD guidelines (OECD, 1998a). These studies were reviewed at the meetings of the Bioethics Commission for compliance with the “Three R’s” principles and Directive 2010/63/EU.

Competing interests

The experiments were paid for by Normopharm LLC, Russia.

Abbreviations

LLC – Limited Liability Company

OECD – Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

GLP – Good Laboratory Practice

GHS – Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals

LD50 – Lethal Dose, 50%, is a standard toxicological measurement indicating the amount of a substance required to kill 50% of a test population

H – hours

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